

THEORETICAL ANALYSIS OF SOMATISMS RELATED TO HUMAN BODY PARTS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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***Annotation.** This article discusses somatic phraseology involving the words eye in Uzbek and English and their comparative analysis. Comparative analysis of somatic phraseological units in Uzbek and English languages is analyzed on several examples. The theoretical data have been processed.*

***Keywords:** somatism, phrase, phraseological unit, phraseology, phraseological unit.*

INTRODUCTION

In linguistics, the term "somatism", which is used to refer to the names of human body parts, was first used by the scientist F. Vakkotmani, who studied Estonian phraseologisms. He noted that somatisms are among the ancient forms of phraseologisms and make up a significant part of the phraseological fund of the Estonian language.

One of our Uzbek linguists, A. Mamatov, quotes the opinion of A. Isaev from his research: "According to A. Isaev, the components "eye", "mouth", "hand", "heart" are considered the most productive in the Uzbek language. The majority of phraseologisms in the Uzbek language are somatic phraseologisms."

MAIN PART

At the current stage of social development, linguistics is developing not only as a set of knowledge about communication and the world, but also as a direction that is considered as a repository of memory reflecting the material, social, spiritual level and achievements, which is an indicator of the culture of the nation. Because language is a means that expresses and embodies the national mentality.

Recently, in many areas of science, it has been observed that man and his related aspects are in the center of attention in research. The anthropocentric paradigm has become the main direction in linguistics.

Somatisms (Greek "soma" - body) are considered one of the ancient lexical layers of any language and occupy an important place in the linguistic landscape of the world due to their universality.

Somatisms are distinguished by the fact that they are the most ancient and mental layer of the vocabulary of any language.

The reason for constant attention to somatisms is that the process of self-awareness and self-perception as a person among the surrounding realities begins with the sensations that arise directly through the body parts.

Although the names of the human body parts exist in all languages, each language representative evaluates the body parts differently, therefore it is a valuable material in studying the linguistic picture of the world.

Since somatisms have been one of the sources of knowledge and understanding of the world since ancient times, such terms have long been used in folk tales - proverbs and sayings, which are considered the beginning of fiction. A comprehensive and in-depth analysis of somatic paremas opens the way for the researcher to enter the linguistic world of the speakers of the language to which the parema belongs.

Somatology is a branch of anthropology that studies the changes in the shape, size and weight of the human body and its parts.

The term "somatism" was first used in linguistics by the Finno-Ugric researcher F. Vak to name Estonian phraseologisms involving human body parts. Somatisms are one of the oldest lexical units in Estonian phraseologisms, the scientist notes. He divided all somatic phraseologisms into three groups: expressions describing only people, expressions describing both people and animals, and expressions describing only animals.

In recent years, somatic phraseologisms have been studied in a comparative plan within the framework of languages of different systems. In this regard, significant achievements have been made in the research of such scientists as Y. Dolgoplov (somatic phraseologisms in Russian, English and German), M. Abilgaliyeva (somatic phraseologisms in Kazakh and German), D. Saypullayeva (somatic phraseologisms in Turkmen and English).

N.A. Bagdasarova's research is devoted to the study of the lexical expression of emotions in Russian and English culture (phraseological lexicon), but it contains information related to somatological lexicon. N.A. Bagdasarova notes that in both languages the most "expressive" part of the body is the face. But the similarity ends there. For the rest of the body, it acquires the opposite meaning in both languages. In Russian, the emphasis is on eye somatism. In English culture, the main emphasis is on the "head" and "body". Although English has many idioms related to "stomach" (turn your stomach, not have the stomach for, get butterflies in your stomach, etc.), in Russian there is only one sign related to "stomach" (sucks under the spoon).

Some features of the expression of emotions in both languages correspond (for example, surprise is better expressed through "eyes", and fear is better expressed through "body" and "legs-hands"). However, these situations are not always the same in both languages. For example, the feeling of hatred in English is expressed using idioms, which include the somatisms "hand", "legs". In Russian, on the contrary, there is no word that names them.

Russian linguist Y. Bashkatova works on ideologies based on somatisms in English and Russian. According to her, somatisms are characterized by having a certain symbolic meaning, reflecting national and cultural views. Bashkatova highlighted that the somatism "back" in English means patience, diligence and work ability, the somatism "neck" means submission, and the somatism "tooth" means a sign of aggression, weapons of attack or defense.

The scientist, having studied somatisms from a linguocultural perspective, emphasizes that they are distinguished by their national specifics, they express the experience of the people speaking a particular language, human qualities. For example, in the linguocultural theory of the English peoples, "stomach" means courage and determination (have the stomach for something, a strong stomach), while in Russian it expresses the concept of "life" (положить живот за кого-н.; класть душу и живот; даровать живот).

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, somatic phraseology is of great importance in English and Uzbek languages. World and Uzbek linguists have thought about somatic phraseology and conducted scientific work on it. With the help of somatic phraseology, it is possible to express the lifestyle, customs and mental and physical states of each nation. In expressing somatic phraseology, the lexemes "head", "hand", "eye", "foot" occupy a special place.

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